

Stability and Phase Plane Analysis of the "Brusselator"

P. N. JHA and R. K. PRASAD*

Department of Chemistry, Bihar University, Muzaffarpur-842 001, Bihar

Manuscript received 17 March 1980, revised 13 October 1980, accepted 29 January 1981

Principles of stability analysis based on Liapounov's first stability theorem have been applied to the "Brusselator" model which involves two intermediates but which is chemically realistic and simplest of all the chemical kinetic oscillatory models. Conditions for the various forms of instability and chemical oscillations in a system, reacting homogeneously as well as inhomogeneously, according to the Brusselator scheme have been obtained which have been found to depend on the relative order of magnitude of the individual rate constants, reactant concentrations and diffusion coefficients of the intermediates.

CONSIDERABLE interest has developed in the theoretical stability and phase plane analysis of chemical oscillation during the recent years¹⁻⁵. The history of such studies begins with Lotka's publications^{6,7} about simple kinetic models leading to chemically unrealistic conservative oscillations. A very realistic kinetic model has been proposed comparatively recently by Prigogine and his co-workers⁸ of the Brussels group and the model termed "Brusselator" leads to oscillations of the limit cycle type.

Twenty-five years ago Hearon⁹ proved that chemical systems obeying linear rate laws (derived from unimolecular mechanism) can not exhibit sustained or damped oscillations whether or not the system is open to flow of matter. Very recently Tyson¹⁰ has shown that bimolecular mechanism involving two intermediates (X and Y) can also not lead to chemically realistic oscillation of the limit cycle type nor can we expect any dissipative structure by including diffusion. Tyson has shown that instabilities can be generated only by involving termolecular mechanism of the type,

the former which is characteristic of Brusselator leads to oscillations around the steady states while the latter can not lead to oscillations unless it is appended by another termolecular step, which then behaves like a trimolecular Lotka-Volterra oscillation.

In the present paper we examine the Brusselator mechanism by making a detailed stability and phase plane analysis based on Liapounov's first method^{11,12} and deduce conditions which lead to instability and oscillations.

Significance of the 'phase plane analysis' :

The kinetic rate laws involving two variables X and Y,

$$\dot{X} = F(X, Y) \text{ and } \dot{Y} = G(X, Y)$$

where F and G are the functions of individual rate constants and concentration terms, correspond to the autonomous system,

$$\frac{dY}{dX} = \frac{G(X, Y)}{F(X, Y)}$$

integrals of which can be represented by curves (trajectories) in the (X, Y) phase plane. Now the steady states (X₀, Y₀) of the system become singular points in the phase plane. Since both $\dot{X}$ and $\dot{Y} \rightarrow 0$ as the singular point is approached, it can be approached asymptotically in the phase plane, but the periodic solutions for the above system of differential equations appear beyond the instability of the steady state, where a closed curve, usually called limit cycle, is approached corresponding to a stable periodic process. In other words in a realistic oscillatory chemical system starting from the neighbourhood of the steady state as the initial condition, the system will attain the limit cycle asymptotically implying that for a sufficient time, X(t) and Y(t) exhibit periodic undamped oscillations. The great significance of this limit cycle behaviour is that the characteristics of these oscillations (amplitude, frequency etc) are independent of the initial conditions unlike an unrealistic conservative oscillatory chemical system where the characteristics depend on initial condition of the steady state. The oscillatory characteristics in the former cases are uniquely determined by the differential equations for the chemical reactions and hence by the kinetic and concentration parameters.

The Brusselator :

This model proposed by Prigogine⁸ which admits

*To whom all correspondences are to be made.

of limit cycle oscillations is as follows :

the net reaction being $A + B \rightarrow D + E$

If diffusion is excluded (system well stirred) this model leads to two non-linear differential equations for the variables X and Y given by

$$\dot{X} = k_1 A - k_2 B X + k_3 X^2 Y - k_4 X \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\dot{Y} = k_2 B X - k_3 X^2 Y \quad \dots (2)$$

where A, B, X and Y denote the concentration terms for the various chemical species and k's are the respective rate constants. This leads to a singular point (steady states of X and Y) in the positive quadrant of the phase plane given by

$$X_0 = \frac{k_1 A}{k_4}; Y_0 = \frac{k_2 k_4 B}{k_1 k_3 A} \quad \dots (3)$$

Since the individual rate constants are not all zero, there is no other singular point.

To examine the stability of the steady states (X_0, Y_0) one considers small perturbations ($x = X - X_0, y = Y - Y_0$) and linearises the equations of motion about the steady states by neglecting the second order terms in x and y. If the perturbations are sufficiently small in the neighbourhood of the steady states one would hope that the behaviour of trajectories is locally like that of linearised equations. This reduces (1) and (2) to the following linear systems with constant real coefficients :

$$\dot{x} \text{ or } \dot{X} = (k_2 B - k_4) x + \frac{k_1^2 k_3 A^2}{k_4^2} y \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\dot{y} \text{ or } \dot{Y} = -k_2 B x - \frac{k_1^2 k_3 A^2}{k_4^2} y \quad \dots (5)$$

which in the standard form can be expressed as

$$\begin{pmatrix} \dot{X} \\ \dot{Y} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \left(\frac{\partial \dot{X}}{\partial X}\right)_0 & \left(\frac{\partial \dot{X}}{\partial Y}\right)_0 \\ \left(\frac{\partial \dot{Y}}{\partial X}\right)_0 & \left(\frac{\partial \dot{Y}}{\partial Y}\right)_0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} \quad \dots (6)$$

where the zero subscript stands for steady state condition.

The solution of this system of differential equations can be found by standard procedure and expressed as :

$$\begin{pmatrix} x(t) \\ y(t) \end{pmatrix} = C_1 f(t) \cdot e^{\lambda_1 t} + C_2 g(t) \cdot e^{\lambda_2 t} \quad \dots (7)$$

where C_1 and C_2 are the mixing coefficients λ_i ($i=1, 2$) is the characteristic root of the associated polynomial

$$\lambda^2 - \text{Tr} \cdot \lambda + \Delta = 0,$$

$$\text{In which } \text{Tr} = \left(\frac{\partial \dot{X}}{\partial X}\right)_0 + \left(\frac{\partial \dot{Y}}{\partial Y}\right)_0$$

$$\text{and } \Delta = \left(\frac{\partial \dot{X}}{\partial X}\right)_0 \left(\frac{\partial \dot{Y}}{\partial Y}\right)_0 - \left(\frac{\partial \dot{X}}{\partial Y}\right)_0 \left(\frac{\partial \dot{Y}}{\partial X}\right)_0$$

The roots will be given by

$$\lambda_{1,2} = \frac{\text{Tr} \pm (\text{Tr}^2 - 4\Delta)^{1/2}}{2}$$

It is not easy to determine the form of the functions f and g in equation (7) but since we are interested only in the behaviour of trajectories, we need to know only the nature of the roots λ_1 and λ_2 . The nature of the singular points of the system (6) which can be classified as nodes, foci, centres and saddle points as well as the form of the trajectories are all to be decided by the roots λ_1 and λ_2 .

Three cases arise :—

(i) λ_1 and λ_2 are real, distinct and $\neq 0$; (ii) λ_1 and λ_2 are both complex conjugates and (iii) λ_1 and λ_2 are equal.

Case (i) arises when $\text{Tr}^2 - 4\Delta > 0$, in which case the solutions are of the form :

$$x(t) = C_1 e^{\lambda_1 t}, y(t) = C_2 e^{\lambda_2 t}$$

where C_1 and C_2 are arbitrary real constants. Now since $\lambda_1 \lambda_2 = \Delta$, and $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = \text{Tr}$, both λ_1 and λ_2 will be of the same sign if $\Delta > 0$, negative when $\text{Tr} < 0$ and positive when $\text{Tr} > 0$. If $\lambda_1 < \lambda_2 < 0$ the steady state (X_0, Y_0) will be an asymptotically stable node and if $\lambda_2 > \lambda_1 > 0$, it will be an unstable node. The trajectories in two cases will be oppositely directed. The orientation of these trajectories will be determined by the values of the constants C_1 and C_2 . If, on the other hand, $\Delta < 0$, λ_1 and λ_2 will have opposite signs making the steady state a saddle point (essentially unstable).

Case (ii) arises when $\text{Tr}^2 - 4\Delta < 0$. In this case the situation $\text{Tr} = 0$ will lead to imaginary values of λ_1 and λ_2 and hence to a stable centre (not asymptotically) with an infinity of circles or ellipses as the corresponding trajectories. If $\text{Tr} \neq 0$, the roots are complex, the trajectories will then be a family of spirals given by the equation

$$x^2 + y^2 = C_1^2 e^{2 \cdot \text{Tr} \cdot t}$$

where C_1 is an arbitrary constant, Tr represents the real part of the complex roots. The steady state (X_0, Y_0) in such a case will be the focus of spiralling trajectories. This will be asymptotically stable if $\text{Tr} < 0$ and unstable if $\text{Tr} > 0$. The direction of increasing time will be determined by the sign of C .

Case (iii) of double root ($\lambda_1 = \lambda_2$) arises when $\text{Tr}^2 - \Delta = 0$. In special case when $\left(\frac{\delta \dot{X}}{\delta Y}\right)_0 = \left(\frac{\delta \dot{Y}}{\delta X}\right)_0 = 0$, the trajectories will be a family of straight lines of the ymx type. The steady state (X_0, Y_0) will be called a proper node, asymptotically stable if $\text{Tr} < 0$ and unstable if $\text{Tr} > 0$. In the general case when $\left(\frac{\delta \dot{X}}{\delta Y}\right)_0 \neq \left(\frac{\delta \dot{Y}}{\delta X}\right)_0 \neq 0$, all the trajectories will be asymptotic to one of the two axes. The steady state will then be called an improper node, and will be stable if $\text{Tr} < 0$ and unstable if $\text{Tr} > 0$.

The above analysis shows that the steady state will be asymptotically stable if and only if both $\text{Tr} < 0$ and $\Delta > 0$. Instability arises when either of the roots λ_1 or λ_2 has a positive real part (Tr), $\Delta > 0$, for nodes, foci and centres by definition. Tyson¹⁰ has shown that for bimolecular reaction mechanism, $\text{Tr} \leq 0$ but for termolecular mechanism, certain values of the termolecular rate constants as well as the steady state concentrations of the intermediates can lead to $\text{Tr} > 0$, i.e., can generate instabilities. In the scheme of the Brusselator, therefore, the autocatalytic step $2X + Y \rightarrow 3X$ is the origin of instability. The steady state will be asymptotically stable only when

$$k_2 B - k_4 - \frac{k_1^2 k_3 A^2}{k_4^2} \quad (\text{i.e., } \text{Tr}) < 0 \text{ and}$$

$$k_1^2 k_4 A^2 \quad (\text{i.e., } \Delta) > 0,$$

When $k_2 B > k_4 + \frac{k_1^2 k_3 A^2}{k_4^2}$ with $k_1^2 k_4 A^2 > 0$, the

steady state will be an unstable node.

The different forms of instability and oscillation resulting from the different correlation of the rate parameters can be deduced as follows :

$$(i) \quad k_2 B = k_4 + \frac{k_1^2 k_3 A^2}{k_4^2}$$

$$\text{and } \left\{ k_2 B - \left(k_4 + \frac{k_1^2 k_3 A^2}{k_4^2} \right) \right\}^2 < 4k_1^2 k_4 A^2$$

(roots λ_1, λ_2 imaginary) lead to conservative oscillations around a stable centre (steady state) which is chemically unrealistic.

$$(ii) \quad k_2 B < k_4 + \frac{k_1^2 k_3 A^2}{k_4^2}$$

$$\text{and } \left\{ k_2 B - \left(k_4 + \frac{k_1^2 k_3 A^2}{k_4^2} \right) \right\}^2 < 4k_1^2 k_4 A^2$$

lead to asymptotically stable focus around which damped oscillations would be possible.

$$(iii) \quad k_2 B > k_4 + \frac{k_1^2 k_3 A^2}{k_4^2} \text{ and } \frac{k_1^2 k_3 A^2}{k_4^2} < 0$$

(roots real and of opposite sign) lead to an unstable steady state of the nature of saddle point.

$$(iv) \quad k_2 B > k_4 + \frac{k_1^2 k_3 A^2}{k_4^2} \text{ with } \frac{k_1^2 k_3 A^2}{k_4^2} > 0$$

leads to chemically realistic sustained oscillations of the limit cycle type around an unstable focus. This is possible in the Brusselator scheme where we assume that X and Y are being produced in the reaction vessel at a constant rate and that X decomposes irreversibly into products. In the phase plane it is possible to draw a closed curve around an unstable node representing sustained oscillations.

Examples of both damped and sustained oscillations [category (ii) and (iv) respectively] can be found in the Bray's reaction¹³ i.e., oscillatory decomposition of H_2O_2 by $\text{IO}_3^- - \text{I}_2$ couple. Bray had originally found that if the reaction were carried out with $[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2] = 0.0327 M$ and $[\text{HIO}_3] = 0.009 M$, a damped oscillation in $[\text{I}^-]$, $[\text{I}_2]$ could be observed with respect to time. When the concentrations of the reactants were increased to $[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2] = 0.190 M$ and $[\text{KIO}_3] = 0.094 M$ and the $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ maintained between 0.08 N and 0.09 N, an undamped (sustained) oscillation in $\frac{d[\text{O}_2]}{dt}$ vs time was observed with a period length of about 10 minutes.

Matsuzaki¹⁴ has recently proposed a comprehensive mechanism for this reaction which when condensed corresponds to the Brusselator scheme for sustained oscillations shown below :

in which we have substituted A and E by HIO_3 , B by H_2O_2 , D by O_2 , X by HIO_2 and Y by HIO . Step 3 is the termolecular autocatalytic step of the Brusselator. By a proper choice of the rate constant values and the concentration of the reactants, they have succeeded in showing through computer simulation a sustained oscillation of $[\text{I}_2]$, $[\text{I}^-]$ and $\frac{d[\text{O}_2]}{dt}$, confirmed experimentally by light absorption and electrode potential measurements.

Including diffusion :

So far we have assumed that the reaction system is perfectly homogeneous in respect of the concentration

of each chemical species. If, however, the system is not stirred the intermediates X and Y will be transported by diffusion. Then the rate equations for X and Y will be

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{X} &= F(X, Y) + D_x \nabla^2 X + D_{xy} \nabla^2 Y \\ \dot{Y} &= G(X, Y) + D_y \nabla^2 Y + D_{yx} \nabla^2 X \quad \dots (8) \end{aligned}$$

where F(X, Y) and G(X, Y) are the right hand sides of equations (1) and (2), X = X(x, t) and Y = Y(y, t), ∇^2 - Laplacian operator (also called the gradient operator) which in one dimension is $\frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2}$, D_x and D_y are the diffusion coefficients of X and Y and they are both ≥ 0 , D_{xy} and D_{yx} are cross diffusion coefficients which may be positive or negative but in general, they are so small in comparison to D_x and D_y , that they may be conveniently ignored. The homogeneous steady states of the system (8) will be given by (3) and the stability analysis of the steady states will be similar to that of the steady states of the homogenised system (1) and (2). The concentrations of X and Y beyond the steady states at any time t will be given by

$$X = X_0 + x \text{ and } Y = Y_0 + y$$

where x and y are the small perturbations in the steady states and are now functions of time and space, i.e.,

$$\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} = f_k(t) g_k(r) \quad \dots (9)$$

where $g_k(r)$ represents the eigenfunctions of the Laplacian operator satisfying the relationship

$$\nabla^2 g_k(r) = -k^2 g_k(r) \quad \dots (10)$$

with a spectrum of eigenvalues k depending on the boundary conditions. Usually k is real so that k^2 is positive. The rate equations (8) in the standard matrix form can now be expressed as

$$\begin{pmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \left(\frac{\delta F}{\delta X}\right)_0 - k^2 D_x & \left(\frac{\delta F}{\delta Y}\right)_0 - k^2 D_{xy} \\ \left(\frac{\delta G}{\delta X}\right)_0 - k^2 D_{yx} & \left(\frac{\delta G}{\delta Y}\right)_0 - k^2 D_y \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix}$$

As described earlier the solution to this equation lies in determining the roots of the equation

$$\det \begin{pmatrix} \left(\frac{\delta F}{\delta X}\right)_0 - k^2 D_x - \lambda & \left(\frac{\delta F}{\delta Y}\right)_0 - k^2 D_{xy} \\ \left(\frac{\delta G}{\delta X}\right)_0 - k^2 D_{yx} & \left(\frac{\delta G}{\delta Y}\right)_0 - k^2 D_y - \lambda \end{pmatrix} = 0$$

$$\text{or } \lambda^2 + \lambda \left(k^2 D_x + k^2 D_y - \left(\frac{\delta F}{\delta X}\right)_0 - \left(\frac{\delta G}{\delta Y}\right)_0 \right) +$$

$$\begin{aligned} & k^4 \left(D_x D_y - D_{xy} D_{yx} \right) - k^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{\delta F}{\delta X}\right)_0 D_y + \left(\frac{\delta G}{\delta Y}\right)_0 D_x \right. \\ & \left. - \left(\frac{\delta F}{\delta Y}\right)_0 D_{yx} - \left(\frac{\delta G}{\delta X}\right)_0 D_{xy} \right\} + \left\{ \left(\frac{\delta F}{\delta X}\right)_0 \cdot \left(\frac{\delta G}{\delta Y}\right)_0 - \right. \\ & \left. \left(\frac{\delta F}{\delta Y}\right)_0 \left(\frac{\delta G}{\delta X}\right)_0 \right\} = 0 \end{aligned}$$

which may be expressed more simply as

$$\lambda^2 + d_1 \lambda + d_2 = 0 \quad \dots (11)$$

where $d_1 = k^2 I_1 - I_2$, $d_2 = k^4 I_3 - k^2 I_4 + I_5$

$$\text{and } I_1 = D_x + D_y ; I_2 = \left(\frac{\delta F}{\delta X}\right)_0 + \left(\frac{\delta G}{\delta Y}\right)_0$$

$$I_3 = D_x D_y - D_{xy} D_{yx}$$

$$I_4 = \left(\frac{\delta F}{\delta X}\right)_0 D_y + \left(\frac{\delta G}{\delta Y}\right)_0 D_x - \left(\frac{\delta F}{\delta Y}\right)_0 D_{yx} - \left(\frac{\delta G}{\delta X}\right)_0 D_{xy}$$

$$I_5 = \left(\frac{\delta F}{\delta X}\right)_0 \left(\frac{\delta G}{\delta Y}\right)_0 - \left(\frac{\delta F}{\delta Y}\right)_0 \left(\frac{\delta G}{\delta X}\right)_0$$

In the Brusselator scheme this equation assumes the form

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda^2 + \lambda \left\{ -k_2 B + k_4 + \frac{k_1^2 k_3 A^2}{k_4^2} + k^2 (D_x + D_y) \right\}^2 \\ + \frac{k_1^2 k_3 A^2}{k_4^2} + \frac{k_1^2 k_3 A^2}{k_4^2} k^2 D_x \\ + k^2 D_y (-k_2 B + k_4) + k^4 D_x D_y = 0 \end{aligned} \quad \dots (12)$$

$$\text{Putting } I_1 = D_x + D_y, I_2 = -(k_2 B - k_4) - \frac{k_1^2 k_3 A^2}{k_4^2}$$

$$I_3 = D_x D_y, I_4 = \left\{ \frac{k_1^2 k_3 A^2}{k_4^2} D_x + D_y (-k_2 B + k_4) \right\}$$

$$I_5 = \frac{k_1^2 k_3 A^2}{k_4^2}$$

we have

$$\lambda^2 + \lambda (k^2 I_1 - I_2) + (k^4 I_3 - k^2 I_4 + I_5) = 0$$

$$\text{or } \lambda^2 + \lambda d_1 + d_2 = 0$$

The roots are then given by

$$\lambda_{1,2} = \frac{-d_1 \pm (d_1^2 - 4d_2)^{1/2}}{2} \quad \dots (13)$$

and as usual the steady states will be asymptotically stable if and only if both $d_1 > 0$ and $d_2 > 0$.

As $k^2 > 0$ usually we need consider only the signs of $I_1 \dots I_5$. The following points have to be noted :

- (i) $I_1 \geq 0$ (since D_x and D_y are both ≥ 0). Further since $D_x \cdot D_y \geq 0$, I_3 must always be ≥ 0 .
- (ii) If $I_5 > 0$ the steady states will be of the form of nodes, foci or centres and if $I_5 < 0$ it will be a saddle point which is always unstable with respect to homogeneous perturbations ($k=0$).
- (iii) As regards I_2 and I_4 it may be either positive or negative depending upon the relative order of magnitude of the individual rate constants.

There are two chances for instability : $d_1 < 0$ and/ or $d_2 < 0$. Thus if the Brusselator is coupled with diffusion then (assuming $D_{xy} = D_{yx} \approx 0$ and rate constants unity the homogeneous steady states ($X_0 = A$, $Y_0 = B/A$) can become unstable (cf. Eqn. 12) if

$$B > 1 + k^2 D_x + A^2 + k^2 D_y$$

or if
$$B > (1 + k^2 D_x)(A^2 + k^2 D_y)(k^2 D_y)^{-1}$$

Such an instability will lead to spatial oscillations in an initially homogeneous reacting system.

Examples of spatial oscillation when diffusion is included is best provided by Belousov-Zhabotinskii (B-Z) reaction. Busse¹⁵ reported that by performing the B-Z reaction in an unstirred inhomogeneous medium a spatial pattern now known as dissipative structure, was obtained. In such a situation oscillations (concentration waves) of Ce(IV)/Ce(III) indicated by the blue/red colour changes developed due to the ferroin indicator, started at one point and were propagated in all directions with various speeds. Busse has analysed this situation and correlated the properties of the waves in terms of diffusion coefficients of the intermediate substances. After a number of oscillations, when a small concentration inhomogeneity appeared, alternate red and blue layers were formed one by one. However, examples of such oscillations in chemistry are very rare.

These analyses lead us to conclude that the stability/instability and oscillations (conservative or limit cycle type) in a chemical kinetic model of the Brusselator type or in fact any model depend on the relative order of magnitude of the individual rate constants as well as the initial concentrations of the reactants. In case of inhomogeneous reacting system such a model can lead to dissipative structures depending on the diffusion coefficients of the intermediate species in addition to the rate parameters.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (P.N.J.) is thankful to U.G.C. for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. R. J. FIELD and R. M. NOYES, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1974, 60, 1877.
2. G. NICOLIS, *Advan. Chem. Phys.*, 1973, 19, 209.
3. R. P. RASTOGI and K. D. S. YADAV, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, 12, 687.
4. R. P. RASTOGI and A. KUMAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14A, 1.
5. R. P. RASTOGI and M. C. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 16A, 272.
6. A. J. LOTKA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1910, 14, 271.
7. A. J. LOTKA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 1595.
8. P. GLANSDROFF and I. PRIGOGINE, "Thermodynamic Theory of Structure Stability and Fluctuations", New York, Interscience, Wiley, 1971.
9. J. Z. HEARON, *Bull. Math. Biophys.*, 1953, 15, 121.
10. J. J. TYSON and J. C. LIGHT, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1973, 59, 4167.
11. B. F. GRAY, Reaction Kinetics, Vol. 1. Special Periodical Reports. The Chemical Society, London, 1975.
12. N. MINORSKY, Non-linear Oscillations, D. Van Nostrand Co., Princeton, 1962.
13. W. C. BRAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 1262.
14. I. MATSUZAKI and T. NAKAJIMA, "Faraday Symposium on Physical Chemistry of Oscillatory Phenomena, The Chemical Society, London, 1974.
15. H. BUSSE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, 73, 750.